

1 Supporting Information

2

3 1. Linear Inverse Model construction

4

5 We recap the theory for LIM construction, following the seminal study of Penland and
6 Sardeshmukh (1995). If the sea surface height data (\mathbf{x}) as a function of time (t) $\mathbf{x}(t)$ can be
7 approximated as a linear system forced by stochastic noise, i.e.:

8

$$9 \quad \frac{d\mathbf{x}}{dt} = \mathbf{L}\mathbf{x} + \boldsymbol{\xi} \quad (\text{S1})$$

10

11 where $\boldsymbol{\xi}(t)$ describes the spatial structure of the white noise, then the best estimate of the
12 linear operator \mathbf{L} is

13

$$14 \quad \mathbf{L} = \ln \left(\frac{\mathbf{C}(\tau)\mathbf{C}(0)^{-1}}{\tau} \right) \quad (\text{S2})$$

15

16 for some lag τ , where $\mathbf{C}(a)$ represents the covariance matrix at lag a . If the model is well
17 described by (S1) then \mathbf{L} will be independent of the choice of τ .

18

19 The covariance matrix of the white noise forcing $\mathbf{Q} = \langle \boldsymbol{\xi}\boldsymbol{\xi}^T \rangle$ can be estimated from the
20 fluctuation-dissipation relation

21

$$22 \quad \mathbf{L}\mathbf{C}(0) + \mathbf{C}(0)\mathbf{L}^T + \mathbf{Q} = 0 \quad (\text{S3})$$

23

24 The leading eigenvectors of \mathbf{Q} indicate where the noise forcing should be concentrated to best
25 match the observations.

26

27 It is convenient to reduce the order of the observations by projecting onto the leading EOFs,
28 firstly to ensure that the covariance calculation is overdetermined, and secondly because we

29 expect that only the gravest modes are likely to obey the pseudo-linear approximation. As
30 such, the state vector \mathbf{x} represents the projection of the original time series onto the first 50
31 EOFs. In this analysis, the first 50 EOFs collectively explain only 25% of the variance in the
32 domain, but nonetheless capture much of the covariance in the core of the jet.

33

34 The normalized root mean square (RMS) error in forecasts of EOF4 produced using equation
35 (S1) but without the stochastic forcing term is shown in Figure S3, relative to persistence and
36 climatology. EOF4 is chosen for the comparison as it closely resembles the long term trend
37 pattern, and represents the leading mode of variability in the region of interest.

38

39 The first four eigenvectors of \mathbf{Q} - the forcing orthogonal functions – are illustrated in Figure S4.

40

41

42 **Figure S1** Normalised root mean square error in the LIM forecast of EOF4 as a function of lead
43 time (pale blue), compared to climatology (grey line) and persistence (dark blue). A normalized
44 difference of zero indicates a perfect prediction, and 'one' means that the prediction has the
45 same skill as climatology.

46

47

48

49 **Figure S2** First four eigenvectors of the noise covariance matrix \mathbf{Q} in equation (S3) – known as
50 the “Forcing Orthogonal Functions” or FOFs. These structures indicate where white noise
51 forcing should be applied to the linear model to best recreate the observations. The fact that
52 the largest signal in each of the FOFs is in the region of the retroflection suggests that the
53 variability in this region is more strongly driven by external forcing than is the case for the
54 meandering downstream of the Agulhas Extension.

55

56

57

58 2. Stochastically forced LIM simulations

59

60 Once **L** and **Q** have been calculated using equations (S2) and (S3), equation (S1) can be used to
61 make simulations of the stochastically forced linear system. An example of the wave
62 propagation along the axis of the Agulhas Extension as simulated in this way appears as Figure
63 2b in the main text. In order to test the hypothesis that the observed trends in sea surface height
64 could be produced by natural variations in a stationary, stochastically forced system, an
65 ensemble of 10,000 30-year long simulations were produced. In 62 of the ensemble members
66 the linear trend in EOF4 was found to be at least as large as observed, corresponding to slightly
67 above 0.5% (Figure S5). If the two-sided hypothesis is considered - that the 30-year trends are a
68 consequence of natural variability in the meandering - slightly more than 1% of ensemble
69 members produced trends greater than the magnitude observed.

70

71

72 **Figure S3** The cumulative probability density of the trend in EOF4 calculated from the
73 ensemble of stochastically forced simulations using equation (S1). Each dot represents one of
74 the 10,000 simulation and the 62 simulations that had larger trends in EOF4 than the observed
75 trends are highlighted in darker blue dots. The observed trend is marked by the vertical line.

76

77 3. Propagation of sea surface height anomalies along the Agulhas Extension

78

79

80 **Figure S4** Hovmöller diagram of the latitude anomaly of the 0.6 m sea surface height contour – a
 81 proxy for the location of the core of the Agulhas Extension – as a function of longitude and time,
 82 for the period 1993 – 2022. The grey box marks the subsection plotted in Figure 2c. The mean
 83 locations of the meander’s troughs are drawn as vertical lines and annotated at the top of the
 84 panels. For guidance a depiction of the mean position of the Agulhas Extension is provided at
 85 the bottom of each panel (grey shading).

86

87

88

89 **Figure S5** A Hovmöller diagram of the sea surface height anomaly along the mean path of the
90 Agulhas Extension taken from the free-running “01deg_jra55v140_iaf” run of the ACCESS-
91 OM2-01 numerical ocean model (Kiss et al., 2020), for the period 1988-1989, displays similar
92 wave propagation to that seen in the observations.

93

94 Kiss, A. E., Hogg, A. M., Hannah, N., Boeira Dias, F., Brassington, G. B., Chamberlain, M. A.,
95 ... & Zhang, X. (2020). ACCESS-OM2 v1. 0: a global ocean–sea ice model at three
96 resolutions. *Geoscientific Model Development*, 13(2), 401-442.

97

98